

Part I: Translation, Literature, and Style

The present work centers on the systematic investigation of the analysis of an author's style in a translational context, how existing theories and debates have informed the discourse: Jean Boase-Beier's stylistic approach (*Translation and Style* 2) and Eugene Nida and Charles Taber's notion of equivalence (12), and proposing a more holistic theoretical framework that facilitates stylistic analysis of translation by recognizing the mediator's interventions (e.g., Laurence Venuti's focus on the translator's visibility (*Invisibility* 8), etc.

Translation serves as a conduit and bridge between different cultures and languages for various purposes. As an activity that involves the rendition of meaning and ideologies, translation is as old as the world (Tanyitiku 2). As a task, it involves the "conversion of a particular written language into a target language" in written form (Ferreira and Schwieter 1). This emphasizes the question of moving across languages, from one culture to another. Aben Ahmed argues that three major qualities should be reflected in an adequate translation (139): it should be accurate, clear, and natural. Studies show that these three constructs are indispensable for the successful communication of the message. In this vision, the translator is the cross-cultural ambassador or mediator navigating the complexities of languages, contexts, and cultures.

Translation presents the negotiations of a degree of tolerance that reckons with differences: it is required when mutual understanding in communication is significantly affected. Whether as an act, an art, or a discipline, as posited by David Katan, translation is bound to the beliefs and values of a given culture (30), with cultural translation defined "as any translation that is sensitive to cultural as well as linguistic factors" (32); since culture is usually viewed as

difference, the indispensability of translation becomes evident when this difference impacts communication in significant ways (Ferreira and Schwieter 17).

Translation as a field has embraced a significant revolution since the term “Translation Studies” emerged, which was coined by James Holmes in his essay (Bassnett and Johnston 13), presented in the Translation Section of the Third International Congress of Applied Linguistics, in August 1972, in Denmark (Holmes 66). The new term draws more scholarly attention to the field as the term enables thinkers to consider its ability to contextualize translation as an independent field, yet capable of relating to all other fields.

Language and aesthetics form parts of the peculiarities of literature, with an attention to its process and product:

Literature, as an art of language or artistic language construction, is characterized by a series of peculiarities which distinguish it from other forms of linguistic communication, shaping the texts which materialize as linguistic objects where special attention is paid to language, both in terms of its production and reception (Tomás and Chico-Rico 115).

The definition above emphasizes one of the properties of literary translation. If the text translation is equally referred to as a literary piece, then the transfer of the source meaning, aesthetic features, and other peculiarities is involved during the translation process. Prior research shows that for many years now, “literary fiction and nonfiction” have remained “central to studies of translation” (Wittman et al. 438); and that “literary translation is considered a porous category” that can simply be referred to “as the product of a translator” who mimics the literary form of an existing text to produce a “work designed to be read as literature.” The practice of this form of translation is extensively argued by both translation researchers and literary translators to be “an ancient and

traditional field of translation” (Rothwell et al. 1). Studies also show that this form of translation has an “essential textual dimension” (Thomás and Chico-Rico 115).

From what precedes, the mediator not only translates word for word, phrase for phrase, and sentence for sentence, but also translates the text in its wholeness, as a genre that merits literariness. The literariness present in the text-translation is influenced by language diversity as well as the choices made by the mediator. For that reason, Eugene Nida and Charles Taber emphasize that “translating consists in reproducing in the receptor language the closest natural equivalent of the source-language message, first in terms of meaning and secondly in terms of style” (12). The definition encompassing the translation of both sense and style reveals that the source text might undergo certain modifications during translation, and the question of style comes to mind during this modification. The current study privileges equivalence over the concept of a mere linguistic correspondence, which might not thoroughly deepen my analyses of cultural representation in a stylistic context.

The style of an author carries both the conscious and unconscious meanings of a text. In her *Translation and Style*, Jean Boase-Beier submits that “literary translation can be seen as the translation of style because it is the style of a text that allows the text to function as literature,” and the style is considered “a direct reflection of the author’s choices” (132). This implies that there is something more than just the message conveyed in a text, which can be easily accessed at the surface. Through the style, we can discover deeper, hidden components and elements of culture accompanying and complementing the totality of the message. Therefore, it is unarguable that the message can be incomplete without the style.

a) **African Literary Translation**

In the African context, identity, language, and translation as tools are all woven into the discourse of literature and translation. Language, identity, and style here are situated within a cultural context and are collectively viewed as a whole, defined identity. In this subsection, I will give a general overview of language as an inherent conduit of identity, and then the usage of language within the translation itself for various purposes.

The culture of a society is mirrored through the language spoken by the society. Existing works of prominent African scholars recognize the positions of thinkers in relation to the question of language throughout various eras in different places around the continent. Mid-twentieth-century thinkers like Ngugi Wa Thiong'o define the relationship that exists between a nation's language and the ideology of the people who speak it (36), advocating for a mental independence of the African society from the colonial presence. Building on the above, Frantz Fanon connects the significance of language with the world and culture (30), language being considered a sword of resistance against external influence. And, African writers use this sword for attacking (14) cultural and religious assimilations, as well as for defending and preserving their heritage. According to him, speaking a language is living the cultural world of that language and being part of the civilization of the language (14). Boris Diop, similarly, throughout his "Écrire en Afrique Francophone, ou l'impossible innocence" (2021), emphasizes that a language is made up of the identity and ideologies of the nation to which it belongs (114). If it is dominated, then the identity and ideologies of such people are dominated.

In addition, language in the African context is more recognized in terms of what it can do: an instrument capable of cultivating a sense of equality among the diverse societies of the world. Later scholars like Bachir Diagne and Wale Adebaniwi argue that "the world of language is a world of inequality and domination" because Pierre Bourdieu's sociological approach to translation

declares this inequality among languages (315). From Bachir Diagne's perspective, using language for translation purposes has an aim: to establish a relationship of "equivalence and reciprocity between the identities" and make these identities stand on a foot of equality so that we can all understand ourselves from language to language (14).

Praising a translation, in essence, will imply praising the equality and plurality of all the languages involved, no domination of one over the other. Bachir Diagne acknowledges the existing notion that translation in the African context is a form of domination vis-a-vis the local language. In his opinion, we should try to remember this form of domination while celebrating translation. But he desires that this domination of the central language over the African (peripheral) languages should come to an end. Every language then becomes central; none is at the peripheries of the world (19). What Bachir Diagne is advocating for is the reconciliation, equality, and horizontality of the plural identities, whereby everyone is considered as being central.

From what precedes, it can be noted that language as a weapon in writing seems like a double-edged sword: first, African writers employing foreign languages in literature or translating African literature into foreign languages make their voices heard in other cultures. Secondly, writing in African languages or translating foreign texts into African languages is not only decoding and exposing the secret of foreign communities but also esteeming African languages, identity, and culture, making them visible, equal to others.

The second aspect of African literary translation relevant to the present study is the two-level interface with translation that the continent has experienced. Paul Bandia describes the relationship between translation and African literature in two phases (21): the pre-writing and post-writing translation phases. The pre-writing translation moment is also known as "writing-as-translation," which implies "intercultural or intermedial writing," in Paul Bandia's words (21–22).

The concept of “writing-as-translation” evidently, significantly considers the act of transforming the African indigenous ideas, oral traditions, etc., into writing. The term identifies writing as an act derived from translating existing cultural and linguistic features, thus portraying writing as a kind of translation. The significance of the “intercultural or intermedial writing” is rooted in the emphasis on the fact that writing a text involves a complex process that mediates between textual, visual, or oral media and different cultures (22).

The pre-writing translation moment reflects the interaction among cultural peculiarities before the pen would ever be put on paper. It is a moment of the writer’s contemplations on how to negotiate between African oral thoughts and writing: that is, original thoughts and the mental process, languages to be used in the writing, etc., serve as the issues that emerge in the writer’s mind before they embark on the actual writing. This could be what I can refer to as the first act of translation, which takes place between the African author’s mind and his or her paper. This first activity implies the author translating these African oral traditions from the mind-level onto a physical paper. In addition, the pre-writing translation phase is confronted with a lot of questions beyond linguistic choices: political issues in relation to the colonial presence and cultural equivalence. Paul Bandia discusses and lists examples of African scholars known for this moment of pre-writing translation (22–23): Chinua Achebe from Nigeria, who chose to write in English; Francophone African scholars such as Ahmadou Kourouma (among others), who engaged with pen, given that the pre-writing translation phase goes with the experience of the Négritude movement (23).

The efforts of Chinua Achebe or Ahmadou Kourouma are contrasted by Wa Thiong’o Ngugi, who contributes through writing in African languages. Literature written in the African languages will eventually be translated into English and other languages. Wa Thiong’o Ngugi

argues that putting African languages into writing will improve literacy among Africans and then upgrade the status of the African languages to become prestigious and equal to the colonial, world languages.

As for the post-writing translation moment, the task is complex. It is usually not just a retranslation but also the translation of another translation, as posited by Paul Bandia: “The translation of African literature, whether self-translation or institutional translation (i.e., a professional translator working with a publisher), has always been a double translation process whereby a fictionalized text—which is itself a translation from oral to written language, from a peripheral language culture to a global language—is in turn translated into another alien language (whether global or not) far removed from the source language culture of the original” (27).

Why the notion of double translation? It is because, first, the African literary works—cultural expressions—undergo the process of being translated or fictionalized from oral languages into the written form. Secondly, (re)translating this written form into other languages is the concept of the post-writing moment. The translator is, therefore, expected to be mindful of the oral nuances present in the African literature rendered into a written form.

b) On Style

In reading African literature, like other world literature, there is more than just what is said: how it is said. African authors have continued to influence their target communities through the translation of their works rich in aesthetics: “poetry, plays, literary books, literary texts, as well as songs, rhymes, literary articles, fiction novels, novels, short stories, poems, and many others” (Tanyitiku 3–4).

The notion of style throughout the present work carries both individual and collective identity. Individual identity is inherent in a writer: this concept of authorial style is also known as

idiosyncrasies—the regular and distinctive manner of language use that is peculiar to an individual author (Kotait 238). And a collective identity, because the individual identity in question shapes and is shaped by the universe of the writer. Universe, in this context, does not only refer to the writer’s experience and history but also his or her society, culture, etc.

Therefore, style is the individual peculiarity, distinctiveness of diction, or sound and word manipulation that is implicitly present in the author’s mind and universe and so manifests (un)consciously in the course of writing. The notion of style, however, earns competing views from various thinkers because some consider it to be core and indispensable, co-constructed by both the author and the translator, while others see it as a problematic aspect in literary translation, etc.

The subject of style is gradually becoming a popular discourse in translation as an interdisciplinary field, especially in contemporary literary translation contexts. Style is now, according to Enaka Tanyitiku, a “trope of literary translation theory and practice” (1). This Enaka Tanyitiku’s claim means that style is central, significant today. Enaka Tanyitiku adds that the style can be considered as the “textual strategies that critique literary texts, explain why certain forms are preferred by writers over others, clarify how figures of speech work, and describe both literary and non-literary texts” (1).

Style is central to literary works as well as to the translation of these works. The favorite style definition of Jean Boase-Beier in her *Translation and Style* accentuates the meaning or cognitive state (132–134) of the speaker in a literary work, characterized as “the perceived distinctive manner of expression” (2). This can, besides linguistic elements, involve both the subconscious and conscious ways of expression attributed to the speaker by the text. However, I contend that the writer of the text, either implicitly or directly, weaves historical and cultural

perspectives into their writing. No text writes itself. Therefore, style can be considered as the (sub)conscious mode of expression a given text assigns to its narrator(s), reflecting some inherent traits of the spirit and universe of the writer of such text.

From what precedes, the source of style is worth debating within the context of translation as a process and a practice. Per Jean Boase-Beier, the relationship of style and translation and the study of translation exist in three forms. First, the translator's understanding of the original text: "In the process of translation, the way the translator understands the style of the source text will affect the way the text is read and understood, and what opinions or attitudes are attributed to its speakers or characters" (*Translation and Style* 1). Second is the translator's style: "the way the target text is written by the translator will also be influenced by the choices the translator makes, and style is the outcome of choice (as opposed to those aspects of language which are not open to choice). So, the translator's style will become part of the translated text" (*Translation and Style* 1). Third is the reader's understanding of the translation's style and its possible relationship to the source text (*Translation and Style* 1).

Apparently, the three forms mentioned above present a chain of complex interactions between style and translation. And "to pay attention to style in the study of translation means to consider how all these factors are reflected in the text and its translation" (Boase-Beier, *Translation and Style* 2). This implies that the question of style is beyond the mere use or choice of language. In translating a text, focus on style has to do with a close reading and holistic analysis, without neglecting the factors discussed above.

One of the differences between writers is their universe. A writer is surrounded by a universe that influences his or her mind during the production of the text. That is, the difference between writers can be traced to their historical, religious, cultural, and figurative perceptions of

the world (Dovletkireeva and Magomadova 1). Known for its aesthetic features, the literary text is made up of imagery shaped by factors mentioned above, unlike non-literary works. An instrumental factor in the process of translating an author's style, as suggested by Gengshen Hu, is preserving the "ecologies of the source text, and vice versa" (249). That is the way to convey the style successfully. The ecologies, in Gengshen Hu's words, expand the definition of the term universe by emphasizing the complex network of relationships between the writer's experience, history, background, culture, etc., and how this web of connections influences the author's mind and creativity.

A style of a (literary) writer is an expression of such an author's ecologies: by this claim, as Hervé Toussaint notes, translation appears to be a sensitive responsibility and commitment (97). In his "Le style en traduction: un aperçu conceptuel," Damola Adeyefa posits that each writer's style is rooted in his or her attitude, culture, and natural point of view (93). If an author's style involves, as Damola Adeyefa asserts, unique "recurrent patterns in linguistic choices, methods" ("Translation" 57), used in a literary text, and if such patterns are a product of his or her mindset (Boase-Beier, *Translation and Style* 133), reshaped by the author's ecologies, then the accurate representation of this style in another language is clearly difficult. My later analyses in the current study will demonstrate how the translator is open to multiple choices due to the difficulties presented by the complexity of the ecologies of author.

Besides the visible recurrent linguistic patterns and methods, the challenging question is how to understand and translate the author's intent in his or her style. Jean Boase-Beier emphasizes that the acceptability of expressions and the connotation of terms change over time (*Translation and Style* 135). Such changes can cause issues for the mediator, such as the following questions:

How can one know what the original author meant over time? How can one interrogate if the connotation of the original author's words has eventually changed at the epoch of translation?

An authorial style is subject to multiple interpretations, and the farther the translator is from the source author's ecologies, the more difficult the translation task becomes. As Luisa Marino asserts, the translator's sociocultural background and other various contexts can make the translation difficult because the translator can only interpret the source text based on his or her own universe and different contexts (A229).

The existing cognitive style of the mediator, influenced by his or her ecologies, is also a source of challenge for translating another writer's style because the former tends to interfere with the latter. The study of Mona Baker et al. tends to emphasize how notable studies have been carried out on the linguistic features of the translator's style in relation to his or her mind (55–76). Also, external influence from other agents, such as the publishers, the original author, directors, editors, etc., negotiates the final decision on the translation (15). And, therefore, the translator's spirit is not the sole decision-maker, though he or she is expected to concentrate on the main tasks of stylistic and thematic comprehension of the source text, harmonizing diverse structures of languages, and harmonizing the structures of the author's style (Adeyefa, "Translation" 64).

There are several constraints on producing or translating the African literature. One of the normative and practical constraints on the production of African literature, according to Babatunde Ayeleru, is that African authors write from a depth of culture, often lacking sufficient appreciative terms in expressing their thoughts literally (9). Here, Babatunde Ayeleru is referring to the African culture and its languages, which are foreign to the colonial languages. This depth of African culture from which African literature is reproduced is not something its writers can exhaust. Therefore, it might be difficult for these writers to always find adequate equivalents in the existing lexicon of

the colonial language they are writing. This sometimes results in the lack of literal expression in the colonial language. The African writers have the option to find a creative, stylistic way to express their worldviews by incorporating African cultural nuances into their works while employing the colonial language(s) as a writing tool.

To translate an African novel is to translate the African's thought, influenced by their universe, and expressed in textual form. This could be a task requiring more effort in order to predict and assume the correct, hidden intention of the novelist. It is (more) challenging if the translator is distant from the original author's universe.

Also, the translation is hardly realized in isolation by the mediator, due to the influence of other factors. The translator is also likely to face the question of who indeed determines the final product. The presence of the publisher, editor, or other circumstances can threaten the quality, approval, and acceptability of the translation, constituting, therefore, many voices instead of the translator's voice alone (Pillière 245). While I acknowledge the issues discussed in this section (i.e., emphasis on the style of an original author), I stand to argue for a visible position of the mediator because his or her interpretive and stylistic choices reshape the product in one way or the other.

c) **On the Translator**

The current subsection centers on the translator's position, personality, and culture in relation to translating the authorial style. I maintain that the translator's personality, style, influenced by his or her ecologies, greatly contributes to the reshaping of the product, thereby revealing his or her contributions through the interpretive process of the original text.

The mediator's presence could be referred to as the possible interventions that create the new text. The style of the mediator can be displayed through his or her interventions. Many

scholars have discussed what Aline Ferreira and John Schwieter refer to as the “Traditional Translation Theory,” which encompasses notions such as the translator’s presence should not be apparent in the translated version (i.e. invisibility); the translator’s position is expected to be neutral and that the translator should avoid any personal interventions of his or her own (i.e. neutrality); and the translator must “remain faithful” to the content and style of the original writer (i.e. author’s intent). One of the fundamental reasons for the Traditional Translation Theory is the emphasis on translation accounts and theories about the need for the faithfulness of translator to the original author’s intent. Thus, the translator is considered a traitor once the translation deviates from the author’s intent. The original author is identified with his or her sole authority (Ferreira and Schwieter 221). These and other factors contributed to hiding the translator.

Disclosing the presence of the translator remains, therefore, a sensitive issue, and this thesis argues for a rethinking of these existing perspectives. One way the translator could be felt in the translation is at the sensitive point of rendering the source style, where there is a possibility that he or she could enhance it or obscure it in the target cultural context. Some basic terms used to indicate the translator’s presence, according to Şehnaz Gürçaglar, include “fingerprints, voice, feel, implicit translator,” and so on (524). However, can it be assumed that the translator is felt throughout the translation? I argue that the question should not be about the absence or the presence of the mediator; it should be about the degree to which his or her presence should be seen in the product, since, inevitably, the translator appears throughout the translation.

The translator assumes a full, notable responsibility. He or she is a target audience and a source of interpretation. He or she is the reader and interpreter of the original and the writer of the newly created text. Thinkers like Jean Boase-Beier support this view of the translator’s position as a premier reader (*Translation and Style* 4): As the mediator, the translator reads the original text

first for himself or herself and then for the target audience. The reading involves a deep interaction with the given text to decode the what, how, where, when, why, etc., of each context. The source text's style affects the translator, and this original effect should be evaluated as well. Secondly, the translator is a writer of the target text; therefore, as an author of the newly written text, he or she determines the choices of style present in the translated version (*Translation and Style* 5).

From what precedes, the translator, as an individual writer, possesses his or her unique way(s) of writing due to his or her training and ecologies, which consequently inform the product: one of the main arguments of the current work. The concept of the translator's choices is what Susan Bassnett emphasizes in her *Translation and World Literature* when she discusses translation as a kind of substitution for the original text. In her opinion, translation is just evidence of "a reader's reading," who himself or herself originates from another epoch, experience, and culture. Translation stands to replace the source text where the latter is inaccessible (3) due to language diversity.

It is arguable to conclude that if a translation finally appears as perfect as the original, then it might not be a translation but the same copy of the original. Therefore, the translator's interventions, as supported by the present study, must be identified and valued. Albaladejo Tomás and Francisco Chico-Rico refer to the notion of substitution as "text edition" since the translation is a newly reproduced text from an existing one. Both substitution and text edition can also be described as a type of "literary criticism" of the original, whereas the translator assumes the responsibility of an exponent of the original and writes another text through critical evaluations of the former. In addition, the critic's absence is not present in the target text, as he or she is the author of the new text (116).

We can now see that the translator, from Albaladejo Tomás and Francisco Chico-Rico's perspective, is not only a reader but also a text producer. The literary translator's aim, as supposed, is to convey the literariness of the original text into the product (117). The existing debate has been around the degree of equivalence, resemblance, and distance, at all levels, between the original and the target texts. Throughout his "Le Style en traduction: un aperçu conceptuel," Damola Adeyefa discusses that, since the translator is a writer, the translator as an individual possesses their own way of writing: style. And the aesthetics, originality, validity, and effectiveness of a literary work are all kept in the author's style (74). This reminds us that the appearance, authenticity, effectiveness, and validity of the text-translation are determined by the mediator's style, the one responsible for the new text.

The debates about faithfulness are tricky because the mediator tends to dismiss the original author's voice at a certain point for one reason or another. It is significant to interrogate how loud the original author's voice seems to be in the translation. The presence of the translator in the new version, in certain ways, has more effect on the intended readers.

Beyond the old debate about faithfulness is the concept of acceptability. What is translation if it is inaccessible, unreadable, and unwelcome to the target audience? What would be the aim of a translation that does not appear linguistic, cultural, and stylistic to the target community? Those and many more questions can make the mediator consciously shape the target readerly effects (Oneț and Ciocoi-Pop 224). Gayatri Spivak's contribution to the discourse of the political power of the translator as a writer can be seen in her *Can the Subaltern Speak?* published in 1988. She acknowledges the importance of the translator and that he or she possesses a certain level of authority over the target text and that such power should be used to (re)present the voice of the Other successfully instead of marginalizing them.

The interference of the authorial style with that of the translator presents certain obstacles, and the current study aims to investigate the obstacles of stylistic translation in the Francophone African context. In practice, two authors are involved: the original and the mediator. The mediator's task is unending, subject to revision, as cultures and other contexts of life evolve. In the next section, I will discuss, from a Francophone African context, the methodology and theories employed in the present study to discuss the stylistic translation and its challenges.

d) Review of Scholarship on Style in Translation

Many scholars like Damola Adeyefa, Luisa Marino, Annalisa Federici, Enaka Agbor Bayee Tanyitiku, etc., have investigated certain aspects of style in relation to translation practice, and these serve as a bedrock for the current research to contribute to the discourse of translation. Style and translation are linked together in translation discourse. Damola Adeyefa's work on "Translation, Stylistics and Imperativeness of Transliteration in African Literary Translation" (2022) examines translation and stylistics as a field. The author discusses the significance of the interdisciplinary connection between stylistics and translation (68) with the aim of proposing possible strategies for translating cultural nuances in African literary works. The findings demonstrate that researching African style vis-a-vis translation involves considering both the *what* and *how* of the text-translation's structure and the possible incongruity emerging from the manipulation of the source text. In the study, Damola Adeyefa suggests that transliteration is arguably the best strategy for investigating an African author's style in a literary work (53). His analyses tend to come from the point of view of Anglophone African authors. So, I built this thesis on his study while extending my analysis to encompass how Francophone African novelists' styles are translated into English.

The source of style, its relevance, and the interaction between stylistics and translation are discussed throughout the present research, drawing on Luisa Marino's "Stylistic Approaches to Translation: An Overview" (2022). Luisa Marino relies on existing studies to examine the source and the development of the interface between Stylistics and Translation Studies (A221). The author base their analysis on selected excerpts from the Italian translation of Sarah Ladipo Manyika's *Like a Mule Bringing Ice Cream to the Sun* (2016) and its source text, to provide general insights into the relationship between Stylistics and Translation Studies, how this interaction can facilitate the translator's task, and the functions of style in the analysis of fiction (A232–A233). Luisa Marino's study describes the evolving field of research where stylistic analysis and translation converge. My current research builds on this study and further encompasses the critique of employing (individual) styles in writing and challenges related to translating the author's style.

Annalisa Federici's study (2023) is like that of Luisa Marino (2022), and it focuses on a stylistic approach to literary translation. Their study is based on the interconnectedness of "periodical, reception and (stylistic) translation studies" (57) to expand ongoing discourses of the French translation of Virginia Woolf's texts. From a translational stylistic point of view, the author analyzes certain translated excerpts published in periodicals and tends to evaluate the various stylistic effects of these selected passages (63). The study indicates that the translation of stylistic elements in those extracts was carried out through two main strategies: domestication and foreignization. My study includes these two strategies in the analyses to appreciate the mediator's interventions. Insights on the significance of cultural mediators and "cultural transfer" drawn from Annalisa Federici's work serve as one of the bases for my arguments on the mediator's presence in the target text, as discussed throughout this study (73).

Annalisa Federici's research is narrowed down to certain translated extracts of Virginia Woolf's works in periodicals in interwar France. I extend their method and strategies to the translation of style within the African literary text, specifically the Francophone literary works. I investigate the styles of Francophone African novelists as could be generally common to the African (non)fictional world of the twentieth century.

The current research investigates the challenges of stylistic translation, and the study of Enaka Agbor Bayee Tanyitiku (2024) builds a foundation for this thesis. Enaka Agbor Bayee Tanyitiku explores the challenges of translating style in the African prose, basing their analysis of the study on 15 excerpts chosen from *Clandestinement votre* by Charles Tsimi, which could contain potentially difficult styles for translation. The author uses Descriptive Translation Studies to collect the qualitative data and uses Descriptive and Inferential Statistics to analyze the quantitative data (7). Both translation and literary theories were employed in the study. The author finds that the writer's diction, voice, and tone present styles that are difficult to translate due to certain constraints, finally suggesting that understanding the source text's culture could be a solution for translating both the message and the style.

Many assumptions in the research are not generalized because they are from a personal point of view, since the author is a potential translator. While building on this research, the current thesis formulates a more comprehensive theoretical framework from both Descriptive Translation Studies and the Manipulation Theory, and the analysis is based on already translated Francophone African texts. Likewise, the discussions in the present thesis are not intended to account for the context of self-translation, either. Therefore, I compare the source texts with the creative interventions of other translators of these (selected) Francophone African novels.

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